

Correlation between BMI and Blood Glucose Level among medical students

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ABSTRACT

Aim: To determine the correlation between serum glucose and body mass index (BMI) in undergraduate students.

Methods: This cross-sectional study was conducted at Kabir Medical College Gandhara University Peshawar and Shaikh Zayed Hospital, Lahore from 1st July 2017 to 31st December 2017. Total 166 students either male or female having age from 18 years to 24 years were selected.

Results: Minimum age of students was 18 years and maximum age was 24 years. Mean age of the students was 19.17±1.5 years, mean BMI was 24.65±6.196 and mean serum glucose level was 126.23±25.56 mg/dl. The Pearson correlation test showed that the level of serum glucose increased with increasing BMI. This positive correlation was statistically significant ($r=0.625$, $P=0.000$).

Conclusion: The positive correlation between BMI and serum glucose levels. Significant difference between mean serum glucose levels of different age groups was detected.

Keywords: Body mass index, Correlation, Serum glucose, Obesity

INTRODUCTION

In general population, adiposity is measured by body mass index (BMI). BMI is calculated as weight in kg, divided by square of height in meters¹. An individual can be divided into different categories according to their BMI i.e. under weight (if BMI ≤18.5), normal weight (if BMI ranges from 18.5–24.9), over weight (if BMI ranges from 25 to 29.9) and obese (if BMI is ≥30)². Increased BMI can be a risk for carcinomas, stroke and heart diseases³.

In patients of type-II diabetics, obesity is a modifiable risk factor. The mechanism by which obesity induces insulin resistance is poorly understood. Several biological products (free fatty acids, leptin, adiponectin, TNF- α and resistin) secreted by adipocytes, which modulated the insulin secretions. Weight of body and insulin action may be responsible for insulin resistance.⁴ It is assumed that there is a +ve correlation between serum sugar levels and BMI.

Obesity is one of the major public health problems globally. In different parts of the world the average BMI is rising few percent/decade, thus fuelling the concern about the effects of increased adiposity on health⁵. So, a study was planned to detect the correlation between BMI and serum glucose among the undergraduates.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This cross-sectional study was conducted at Kabir Medical College Gandhara University Peshawar and Shaikh Zayed Hospital, Lahore from 1st July 2017 to 31st December 2017. Total 166 students either male or female having age from 18 years to 24 years were selected. Students with any systemic disease were excluded from the study. History was taken from all the students regarding family history of diabetes mellitus. Weight and height of all the patients was measured by weighing machine and measuring tape to calculate BMI. Random blood sample was drawn and sent to laboratory for serum glucose levels. Findings of the

laboratory test and BMI was entered on pre-designed proforma along with demographic profile of all the students. All the collected data was entered in SPSS version 20. Mean and SD was calculated for age, BMI, serum glucose level. Frequencies were calculated for gender and family history of DM. Pearson correlation test was applied to check the correlation between BMI and serum glucose levels. Stratification was done for age, gender and family history of DM. Post stratification student t test was applied to detect the difference of serum glucose levels for these variables. P value ≤0.05 was considered statistically significant.

RESULTS

Total 166 students were selected for this study. Minimum age of students was 18 years and maximum age was 24 years. Mean age of the students was 19.17±1.5 years, mean BMI was 24.65 ± 6.196 and mean serum glucose level was 126.23±25.56 mg/dl. The Pearson correlation test showed that the level of serum glucose increased with increasing BMI. This positive correlation was statistically significant [$r=0.625$, $P=0.000$] (Table 1).

Students were divided into two age groups i.e. age group 18-20 years and 21-24 years. Total 160 students belonged to age group 18-20 years and only 6 students belonged to age group 21-24 years. In age group 18-20 years, mean serum glucose was 126.96±25.68 mg/dl. In age group 21-24 years, mean serum glucose level was 106.33±9.24 mg/dl. Statistically significant ($P=0.025$) difference of mean serum glucose between both age groups was noted (Table 2).

Male patients were 77 and female patients were 89. Mean serum glucose level of male students was 128.64±26.24 and mean serum glucose level of female students was 124.15±24.92. The difference of mean serum glucose levels between male and female patients was statistically insignificant with p value 0.714 (Table 3).

Total 91 students found with family history of DM and 75 students found without family history of DM. Mean serum glucose level was 124.23±25.50 mg/dl in students with family history of DM and 128.65±25.59 mg/dl without family history of DM. The difference between mean serum

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glucose level between both groups was statistically insignificant with p value 0.813 (Table 4).

Table 1: Correlation of BMI with serum glucose

	Serum glucose (mg/dl)	
	Pearson correlation (r)	P-value
BMI	0.254	0.009

Table 2: Comparison of mean serum glucose level between the both age groups

Age (years)	n	Mean±SD	P value
18-20	160	126.96±25.68	0.025
21-24	6	106.33±.24	

Table 3: Comparison of mean serum glucose level for gender

Gender	n	Mean±SD	P value
Male	77	128.64±26.24	0.714
Female	8	124.15±24.92	

Table 4: Comparison of mean serum glucose level for gender

Family history of DM	n	Mean±SD	P value
Yes	91	124.23±25.50	0.813
No	75	128.65±25.59	

DISCUSSION

In current study a positive correlation ($r = 0.254$) between serum glucose and BMI was detected. In different studies of the world, positive correlation was also detected between serum glucose and BMI.^{6,7} Ethnicity also affects the association between diabetes mellitus and obesity which may explain the various levels of association between the serum glucose levels and obesity reported by different studies.⁸

In age group 18-20 years, mean serum glucose was 126.96±25.68 mg/dl. In age group 21-24 years, mean serum glucose level was 106.33±9.24mg/dl. Statistically significant ($P=0.025$) difference of mean serum glucose between both age groups was noted.

Increasing incidence of obesity globally is attributed to dietary habits and changing in life styles⁹. The mechanism by which obesity induces insulin resistance is poorly understood. Obesity causes peripheral resistance to insulin-mediated glucose uptake and may also decrease the sensitivity of the beta-cells to glucose¹⁰. These changes are largely reversed by weight loss, leading to a fall in blood glucose concentrations towards normal levels. Weight gain precedes the onset of diabetes; conversely, weight loss is associated with a decreased risk of type 2 diabetes^{11,12}.

The administration of resistin, an adipocyte derived hormone, decreases while the neutralization of resistin increases insulin-mediated glucose uptake by the adipocytes. Thus, resistin may be a hormone that links obesity to diabetes⁴. Leptin is produced by adipocytes and is secreted in proportion to the adipocyte mass. It signals the hypothalamus about the quantity of stored fat. Studies in humans and animals have shown that leptin is associated with obesity and insulin resistance¹³. The deficiency of adiponectin, an adipocyte-derived hormone, plays a role in the development of insulin resistance and subsequently, type 2 diabetes¹⁴.

Retinol-binding protein 4, free fatty acids, tumour necrosis factor-alpha, plasminogen activator inhibitor 1, interleukin-1 beta, uncoupling protein 2 and obestatin are also implicated in the adipose tissue induced pathogenesis of type 2 diabetes¹⁵.

Body mass index is a good measure of adiposity; however, the relationship between actual body fat and BMI differs between ethnic groups, and as a consequence, the cut off points for the overweight status and obesity based on BMI, will have to be ethnicity specific¹⁶.

CONCLUSION

Findings of current study showed a positive correlation between BMI and serum glucose levels. Significant difference between mean serum glucose levels of different age groups was detected. There is insignificant difference between male and female students.

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